

The Zenith seen through the Oculus of the Pantheon

Amelia Carolina Sparavigna

Politecnico di Torino

Abstract: Using Stellarium, an open-source free-software planetarium, we can simulate the night sky at the Zenith of Rome, and the stars visible through the Oculus of the Pantheon.

Keywords: Archaeoastronomy, Zenithal Passage of Stars, Stellarium.

The Pantheon is an ancient Roman temple. The present building, used today as a church, was completed by the Emperor Hadrian and probably dedicated about 126 AD [1]. The building is circular, having a portico with columns of Corinthian granite. The Pantheon dome is made of concrete [2]. At the top of the dome there is an Oculus, a round opening which is the main source of natural light inside the temple (Figure 1). The oculus has a diameter of 9 m, whereas the building is 43 m tall [1].

Figure 1 – The coffered concrete dome of the Pantheon in Rome, with a central opening (oculus) to the sky, as seen from satellite (courtesy: Google Maps).

The Pantheon is the subject of several works discussing the link between its architecture and astronomy. In a short pamphlet for instance [3], Fausto Masi proposed the Pantheon as an astronomical instrument, to determine the altitude of the sun. The pamphlet is containing sketches showing the position of the shaft of sunlight passing through the roof at the solstices and the equinoxes (the Figure 2 shows a drawing inspired by a sketch in [3], concerning equinoxes).

Figure 2: An example of drawings that we can see in Ref.3.

In fact, among the several references about the Pantheon [4-15], some of them are concerning the sun and the light entering the temple. Here we propose to consider the Oculus for observing the night sky and the stars which are passing at the Zenith of Rome. Let us remember that the sun and the moon, at the latitude of Rome, cannot reach the zenithal position. If we are precisely at the center of the floor, through the oculus we can see an angle 10 degrees wide, as given in the Figure 3. Let us use Stellarium, a planetarium software that shows exactly what we can see when we look up at the stars.

Figure 3: The Pantheon is 43 m tall. The diameter of the dome is of 43 meters. The Oculus has a diameter of 9 m. If we are at the center of the floor, we can see an angle 10 degrees wide.

The Stellarium software can show us the bright stars near the Zenith. Let us simulate the sky during a night of 126 AD, the year of the probable dedication of the temple. In the following figures, the circle is at 10 degrees from the Zenith. If we consider D the diameter of this circle of Stellarium, the Oculus has to be imagined appearing with $D/2$.

Figure 4: On the left, 20 May, 126 AD (Vega); on the right, the same night, after two hours (Deneb).

Figure 5: On the left, 20 September, 126 AD (Mirphak); on the right, the same night, after one hour and 35 minutes (Capella).

An observer in the temple was able to see the zenithal passage of these stars during the year. Therefore, the temple could also be used to measure the time, during the night, observing the stars visible through the Oculus. Let us conclude telling that, due to the precession of the Earth's axis, Capella that passed through the Zenith of Rome in the second century AD, today is not a zenithal star (Figure 6).

Figure 6: Today, Capella has not a zenithal passage.

References

- [1] Terenzio, Alberto (1935). Pantheon. Enciclopedia Italiana. Available from [http://www.treccani.it/enciclopedia/pantheon_\(Enciclopedia-Italiana\)/](http://www.treccani.it/enciclopedia/pantheon_(Enciclopedia-Italiana)/)
- [2] Sparavigna, A. C. (2014). Some Notes on Ancient Concrete. *International Journal of Sciences*, 3(2), 1-6.
- [3] Masi, F. (1996). The Pantheon as an Astronomical Instrument. EILS. Roma.
- [4] Lim, C. S. (1998). The Formal Analysis of Pantheon in Rome in Relation to the Solar Angles. *Journal of architectural history*, 7(4), 191-198.
- [5] de Fine Licht, K. (1968). The Rotunda in Rome: a study of Hadrian's Pantheon. Jutland Archeological Society.
- [6] Joost-Gaugier, C. L. (1998). The iconography of sacred space: A suggested reading of the meaning of the Roman pantheon. *Artibus et Historiae*, 21-42.
- [7] MacDonald, W. L. (2002). The Pantheon: design, meaning, and progeny. Harvard University Press.
- [8] Meeks, C. L. V. (1960). Pantheon paradigm. *Journal of the Society of Architectural Historians*, 19(4), 135-144.
- [9] Nicoletta, L., & Virgili, P. (2016). The Urban Set of the Pantheon and the Mausoleum of August in Rome, between Architectural and Astronomical Symbolism. *Mediterranean Archaeology and Archaeometry*, 16(4), 249-255.
- [10] Wilkins, P. (2004). The Pantheon as a globe-shaped conception. *Nexus Network Journal*, 6(1), 78-84.
- [11] Sperling, G. (1997). Das Pantheon in Rom, Abbild und Mass des Kosmos. *Ars Una*, ISBN-10: 389391854X, ISBN-13: 978-3893918546
- [12] Sperling, G. (2004). Early Orchestration: The Pantheon as a resonance element. *Nexus Network Journal*, 6(1), 65-69.
- [13] Sperling, G. (2015). The "Quadrivium" in the Pantheon of Rome. In *Architecture and Mathematics from Antiquity to the Future* (pp. 215-227). Springer International Publishing.
- [14] Martines, G. (2000). The relationship between Architecture and Mathematics in the Pantheon. *Nexus Network Journal*, 2(1-2), 57-62.
- [15] Hannah, R. (2009). The Pantheon as a timekeeper. *British Sundial Society Bulletin*, 21(4), 2-5.